

P17. A CERAMIDE-BASED *STRATUM CORNEUM* SUBSTITUTE: TOWARDS A NOVEL *IN VITRO* PERMEATION SCREENING TOOL

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ABSTRACT

Skin topical administration and percutaneous permeation are appealing bioactive delivery routes, but they present challenges that must be carefully addressed during formulation development. As a result, an increasing number of researchers are working to create cutting-edge, economically viable, and successful *in vitro* percutaneous permeation models for the early stages of pharmaceutical, drug formulation, and cosmeceutical development.

The barrier provided by the Stratum Corneum (SC) intercellular lipid matrix, which is primarily composed of ceramides (CERs), cholesterol (Chol), and free fatty acids (FFA), poses the most difficult challenge for topically administered bioactives. These components are intricately organized in the intercellular lipid matrix in two crystalline coexisting lamellar phases with typical repeating distances of 13 and 6 nm (long periodicity phase (LPP) and short periodicity phase (SPP)). The current study's main goal was to create an innovative, well-standardized SC substitute (SCS) with an intercellular lipid matrix model for percutaneous permeation studies. In this regard, a CER-based lipid model was created and biophysically characterized in various lipid assemblies, including monolayers, bilayers, and liposomes. Surface-pressure isotherms, UV-Vis reflection spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry, Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR), Brewster Angle Microscopy, and Atomic Force Microscopy were used to test the CERs-based lipid mixture's ability to mimic the SC complex organization. The SCS was then embedded in various membrane scaffolds, characterized using ATR-FTIR and X-ray diffraction, and visualized with confocal, atomic force, scanning electron, and Raman microscopy. Finally, SCS was used as an *in vitro* percutaneous tool to assess percutaneous permeation of two bioactive compounds (diclofenac and caffeine). The results were compared to published data and showed promising results, implying that the SCS could be used in both pharmaceutical and cosmeceutical development in a controlled and reproducible manner.